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The process of creating an author's picture book: a method of investigating and interpreting the book's space

Abstract: The article examines the theoretical and practical aspects of mastering book space in the creation of an author's picture book. It defines the theoretical foundations of book space and methods for its organization. The process of developing an author's picture book is presented as a form of practical work for students specializing in Graphics in order to familiarize them with book space. The methodological basis for the artistic organization of book space includes developing ideas and layouts, designing character images, and creating a series of compositional and artistic images. The article presents innovative methods for designing and organizing book space that contribute to the development of spatial and imaginative thinking, the mastery of creative work methods, and the development of professional competencies.

Keywords: book, author's picture book, book space, picture plane, book structure.

Rezumat: În articol sunt analizate aspectele teoretice și practice ale explorării spațiului cărții în procesul de creare a unei cărți de autor ilustrate. Sunt definite bazele teoretice ale spațiului cărții și metodele de organizare a acestuia. Procesul de elaborare a unei cărți ilustrate de autor este prezentat ca o formă de activitate practică pentru studenții specialității Grafică, în vederea însușirii spațiului cărții. Fundamentele metodologice ale organizării artistice a spațiului cărții includ dezvoltarea conceptului și a machetării, proiectarea personajelor și realizarea unui ansamblu de compoziții expresive. În articol sunt prezentate metode inovatoare de proiectare și organizare a spațiului cărții, care contribuie la dezvoltarea gândirii spațiale și imagistice, la stăpânirea metodelor creative de lucru și la formarea competențelor profesionale.

Cuvinte-cheie: carte, carte de autor, spațiul cărții, plan vizual, construcția cărții.

The problem of teaching and perceiving the organization of book space as a cohesive artistic work, where every detail matters, is one of the most complex and under-researched areas in the theory and methodology of teaching book graphics. The relevance of our study is due to the lack of a systematic approach in this field. Currently, the teaching of book graphics in Moldovan higher education largely depends on the lead instructor for specialized disciplines and primarily involves creating individual illustrations, as well as designing the cover, title page, and running heads. Only in exceptional cases is a comprehensive book project realized, which includes design development, layout, and illustrations.

The high demands placed on the educational process in the field of book graphics and artistic disciplines as a whole necessitate a reassessment of the content, forms, and methods of teaching. Researchers and practitioners in art education are focused on developing and implementing modern and flexible teaching methodologies based on the latest scientific achievements in pedagogy, psychology, and methods of teaching visual arts. Improving the training of highly qualified specialists in the field of visual arts, who possess developed creative and artistic abilities, requires the exploration of innovative educational systems.

The aim of this study is to determine the significance of picture books in the educational process and to reveal their role in mastering book space. The research will examine the theoretical foundations of book space and analyze picture books, as well as explore the experience of organizing verbal and iconic elements within book space. Additionally, effective approaches to their composition and integration into a cohesive artistic work will be identified. Based on this data, a methodology will be proposed that considers the interaction between images and text, the structure of spreads, the composition of elements, and the use of space to create an expressive and harmonious perception of the book.

Theoretical Foundations of Creating Picture Books. As P. Rodkin notes, “for many reasons, today the world is being visualized. The text is filled with images”. He continues: “Objectively, a text cannot exist without visual compensation, but visual structure does not exist without textuality; otherwise, it is simply meaningless...” [4]. The illustrative component in modern books, especially in children’s literature, has ceased to be merely an addition to the text and has become an integral part of its structure, where “the image comes first, and the letter comes second” [3, pp. 54-58]. Picture books create such structures, embodying a complex dynamic relationship of creative tension and communication.

The development of the picture book as a genre is associated with the emergence of the term *picture-book* in English literature in the second half of the 19th century. It is formed, as noted by D. Sergeev, “with certain characteristics: the synthetic unity of illustration and text, their specific placement in relation to each other, consideration of age-related features when creating the work, the compositional features of the illustration, and a number of others” [5, p. 400].

The creative experiments of illustrator-artists aimed at finding new expressive means and forms in picture books have blurred the boundaries between literary and visual arts. The picture book has truly become a complex system, as it is based on two sign systems: verbal and visual, where word and image are inextricably linked and interact equally. Martin Salisbury and Morag Styles note that the narrative in a picture book unfolds through the sequential use of illustrations, and in this approach the text plays a subordinate role to the image [1, p. 7].

Book space is a unique environment for perceiving and interpreting a literary work, created through the synthesis of text and graphic form, extending beyond the physical characteristics of the book. It is not merely pages with text and illustrations but a mul-

ti-faceted artistic object, where each element – from font to format – shapes a special world of narrative. It operates not only with text and images but also with the physical space of the book – pages, spreads, margins, and white spaces – transforming them into a unified dynamic structure, creating a unique aesthetic and emotional environment.

Book space is a complex concept that includes the physical, visual, and content components of a book. It encompasses the following aspects:

Physical space is defined by the combination of format, margins, fonts, internal layout, composition of spreads, and the interaction with the sequential arrangement of pages and inserts.

Visual space is formed through illustrations, color palette, and graphic design to achieve aesthetic and functional balance, enhancing emotional perception and expanding the semantic horizons of the text.

Literary space is organized directly through narrative storytelling, structure, and style of the author’s exposition. It represents the fictional or real world where events unfold and characters possess thoughts, experiences, and feelings. In modern editions, interactive elements of augmented reality and QR codes can be embedded into the main content.

Emotional space is formed in the reader at the moment of interaction with the text, visual elements, and their imagination, complementing and expanding the world created by the author and artist, thereby creating their unique emotional space. The reader’s ability to perceive and assimilate information is directly related to the organization of text and visual elements and the feelings and emotions experienced.

All these aspects are interconnected and actively influence one another. For example, physical space directly affects the organization of visual space, which in turn has a decisive impact on the perception of literary space, enhancing the emotional response.

Book space serves as an important tool in education and cultural development, stimulating creative and critical thinking. A deep understanding of the principles and mechanisms of organizing book space forms the foundation for teaching students in the fields of book design and illustration.

Developing an Author’s Picture Book as a Method for Mastering Book Space. The process of creating a picture book is an effective educational methodology that promotes the development of students’ skills in organizing book space. By integrating word and image into a cohesive artistic work, students grasp the fundamental principles and mechanisms of interaction between graphic forms, literary content, and physical space. In a picture book, where the illustrative component transitions from a subordinate

source of information to an equal partner with the text, students can more quickly adapt and acquire the necessary skills. An author's picture book serves as an ideal platform for students, allowing them to express their creative individuality and avoid the constraints associated with interpreting others' work.

Training in designing an author's picture book involves several preparatory moments: (1) *Theoretical foundation*: this includes having a deep knowledge of the history of book construction, typography, composition theory, and color theory; (2) *Practical assignments*: these entail analyzing successful and unsuccessful examples of existing picture books, learning to work with the text, creating sketches, developing book layouts, and mastering various graphic techniques and their combinations.

Modern methods of teaching illustration and the creation of picture books blend traditional and innovative approaches. Traditional methods encompass academic fundamentals such as studying composition, drawing, painting, and mastering various graphic techniques. At the same time, the introduction of innovative methods, including the use of digital technologies, computer programs, and project-based learning, fosters the development of creative thinking, design skills, and proficiency with modern digital tools. The combination of these approaches ensures the comprehensive spiritual, creative, and aesthetic development of students, helps them find unconventional solutions to creative challenges, delves deeper into the profession, and maintains their interest in learning.

Practicing the Mastering of Book Space. The pedagogical process of creating an author's picture book involves immersing students in the specifics of visual storytelling, starting with the formation of a conceptual foundation. At the initial stage, creating a detailed description of the concept, choosing a theme and genre, and developing the plot is the key. Before starting to write the script, it is important to identify the target audience and consider age-related aspects of content perception.

Stages of Developing an Author's Picture Book:

I. The *Plot Development* stage involves creating a script and a visual narrative. It is important to note that the foundation of any picture book is the action – an event expressed through images. Since action is revealed in the book through a sequence of events, abstract concepts are virtually excluded in this genre. Ideally, illustrations should convey meaning so that the content of the book may be understood even without words, with the visual narrative leading the text. Creating the script entails a fascinating story with unexpected twists and an unpredictable ending. It is crucial for the plot to remain cohesive and follow

a single narrative line with a clear sequence of events.

II. The *Layout Development and Artistic Design* stage involves creating a “storyboard” – a visualization of the concept through sketches, which allows the author to obtain a holistic view of the book and to facilitate a more effective project implementation. To ensure that the narrative remains coherent and cohesive, the storyboard should follow the following scheme: 1) the beginning – setting up an intrigue; 2) the development of action in stages, without gaps, maintaining the sequence of events; 3) the resolution, conclusion, and moral. Each illustration should logically flow from the previous one and prepare the viewer for the next one.

In working on the storyboard, a special creative approach is essential, requiring a deep analysis of the content, an ideological concept, and the possibilities for interpretation through graphic images. Students should focus on selecting subjects for the expressiveness of the compositional solutions of future illustrations and organizing spreads, utilizing dynamics and “white pauses” (empty space) for semantic emphasis. It is important to consider that the interaction of the reader with the book space occurs through its composition and dynamics, color palette, and text presentation. A well-structured composition directs the reader's gaze and creates a kind of “route” for perceiving the interaction of words and images. One way to solve complex compositional tasks is through the conscious use of spatial techniques: dynamics and statics, perspective and scaling, color contrasts, textures, and interesting angles.

The second stage of visual design involves character and environment development, selecting appropriate artistic forms, artistic style, and stylization. Working on the character begins with an abstract image that gradually gains individuality-personality, character, and emotions. Natural sketches and drafts, gestures and poses will help achieve expressiveness and dynamism in an image.

III. The *Creative Realization of the Project* – The creative realization of the project involves creating illustrations and a layout of the original work. At the initial stage, the format is chosen, and a preliminary layout is created – which organizes the overall composition of the book, helps determine the placement of illustrations and text, and allows for font selection in order to ensure a harmonious combination of visual and textual content. In this case, the text will be viewed as a component of the overall composition – a visual object that harmonizes with the image. A common mistake is attempting to write the story in words and then create illustrations that would duplicate each other. It is important to understand that the text and

the image are two different languages that can convey the same idea in different ways. This mistake can be avoided by separating the functions of the text and image. The text can describe events, thoughts, and the personality of a character, while the illustration shows how this looks in reality or in the artist's imagination, creating the mood and the atmosphere.

Illustrations are developed according to the specified format and the storyboard, always taking into account the space for text placement. The work on illustration begins with a sketch, adding details and refining the character of the figures. At this stage, it is important to avoid repetition and monotony in a composition building. Using diverse angles and various color relationships helps create tension and a dynamic rhythm, which, according to E. Adamov, "is the sound of the book's composition, permeating the structure and composition of the book, and helps fully reveal its content" [2, p. 6].

The use of mixed graphic techniques (watercolor, ink, pencil, colored pencils, printing, and digital techniques) will give the illustrations special expressiveness and uniqueness. The choice of specific techniques for creating illustrations depends not only on the narrative plot and task, but also on the artist's style and creative preferences.

The construction also plays an important role in creating a picture book, as does the choice of the spread format, especially in the accordion book format, providing the students with an opportunity to explore ways of organizing book space. The book in its unfolded form allows one to see the entire story at once and helps students better understand its structure, composition, and logic of development in motion. They can visually see how illustrations on different spreads interact with each other, how they are united by a common compositional line, and how this affects the perception of the story. In practice, the spread format allows for experimenting with the dynamics of storytelling, creating interesting visual transitions from one spread to another.

IV. *Technical and Production Aspects of the Project*. This section involves the use of software for a final layout, color correction, and the preparation of materials for printing.

Conclusions: Creating an author's picture book is a powerful tool that helps students master the principles of organizing book space, develop graphic story-

telling skills, and foster original graphic solutions and unconventional thinking. Despite the seemingly simple organization of a picture book, the process of its creation is quite complex and requires students not only to have a creative approach but also to possess specialized skills – such as the ability to construct and evaluate the depth of a story, achieve unity between the text and images, and create expressive images and narrative illustrations.

Working with the spread system in the accordion book format allows the students to develop spatial thinking and the ability to visualize a story in three dimensions, helping them understand how compositional and narrative lines operate.

By going through all the stages of book creation, from the initial concept to the finished product, students learn to plan their work, achieve set goals, make independent decisions, and have the opportunity to develop artistic thinking and specific professional competencies.

REFERINȚE BIBLIOGRAFICE:

1. Salisbury M., Styles M. *Children's Picture books: The Art of Visual Storytelling*. London: Laurence King, 2012. 192 p.
2. Адамов Е. Б. *Ритмическая структура книги*. Москва: Книга, 1974. 94 p.
3. Лисицкий Э. *Книга с точки зрения зрительного восприятия – визуальная книга*. Цит. по кн.: Лаврентьев А. *Лаборатория конструктивизма*. Москва: Грант, 2000. 256 p.
4. Родькин П. *Новое визуальное восприятие*. Їп: Зелёная лампа, № 1/2005-2006, «Я» И «ДРУГОЙ». Pe: <https://jgreenlamp.narod.ru/textual.htm> (Accesat la 18.01.2025)
5. Сергеев Д. *Что мы читаем? К определению детской книжки-картинки*, Забайкальский Государственный Университет. Чита, *Детские чтения*, 16 (2), 2021, pp. 400-415. Pe: <https://doi.org/10.31860/2304-5817-2019-2-16-400-415> (Accesat la 18.01.2025)
6. Шаляпин О. В. *Методические особенности обучения живописи студентов художественно-графических факультетов при изображении головы и портрета*. Pe: <https://www.disscat.com/content/metodicheskie-osobennosti-obucheniya-zhivopisi-studentov-khudozhestvenno-graficheskikh-fakul> (Accesat la 10.12.2024)